

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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INTRODUCTION

The Training Guide is the second Deliverable of WP4 “Deployment and Operation” of the RECAP project. Its purpose is to provide Pilot organisations and participants with the necessary skills to install and test the RECAP platform. This is a necessary task for the proper testing and validation of the RECAP Platform (Pilot) in an operational environment in the five pilot countries.

Indeed, training of participants is a requested activity that is planned in the pilot phase as described below:

Training of participants will be conducted across the 5 participating countries and will mainly rely on a common methodology based on the following aspects:

a) Involving the local team in charge of implementing the Pilot. Its members will ensure the following roles in the frame of training activities:

- ✓ **Pilot coordinator:** definition of local training strategy, setting up of internal procedures.
- ✓ **Facilitator:** responsible for the correct development of training sessions.
- ✓ **ICT specialist:** installation of the RECAP Platform, technical support at local level.
- ✓ **Other staff:** support for the production of local training materials, support for the organization of training sessions.

b) Ensuring technical support:

- **ICT specialists** from each local team will provide participants with technical support;
- The **technical desk** (DRAXIS and NOA) will provide permanent support to the ICT specialists (e.g. installation of the RECAP Platform, etc.).

c) Providing the 5 participating country with a general Training Guide that will provide users with the necessary information and skills to use all functionalities of the different modules of the RECAP platform, independently to the type of users, the country, etc. This general Training Guide will be the main Training Material. It will be built as a practical document, with clear and precise instructions, that each participating country will be able to use as a basis for producing its own Training Guide and/or any other Local Training Materials.

d) **Implementing local training strategy.** Each participating country will define its own local training strategy (framework of the training sessions, type of local training materials, etc.) and produce its corresponding **local training materials**. Indeed, each participating country will produce local training materials adapted to their context and specific needs; and translated to national language. Based on each **local training strategy**, the local team will choose either adapting and translating the general Training Guide, or complementing it with Local Training Materials in local language.

Local training strategies and the description of their corresponding local training materials can be seen in **Appendixes 1-5**.

As a preliminary recommendation, users of the RECAP Platform need basic IT skills for registering, signing in and using it, as well as for downloading, the mobile application.

In order to facilitate the training of participants in the use of the RECAP platform, the present **general Training Guide** is divided in the following Chapters:

- **Chapter 1:** System Requirements, Problem Reporting and Technical Support.
- **Chapter 2:** Access to the RECAP Platform.
- **Chapter 3:** Training Guide for Farmers / Agricultural Consultants.
- **Chapter 4:** Training Guide for Inspectors.
- **Chapter 5:** Training Guide for Paying Agencies.

This general Training Guide is a common document that describes the different functions and services of the RECAP Platform. It takes into account the differences which exist between the different participating countries (Greece, Spain, Lithuania, U.K. and Serbia), as well as the different type of users (Farmers / Agricultural Consultants, Inspectors / Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies).

It has been built as a visual guide with the aim of facilitating users to work with the platform, describing usual workflows or functions and providing detailed description of its facilities according to user type.

Within chapters 3, 4 and 5, a common structure / methodology have been used for describing the different services and functions independently of the user and the country. Below, you will find some clues to well understand how information from these chapters is structured and presented.

Each of these Chapters will show the following sub-sections:

- 1) A **brief description** of the type of users and its use of the RECAP Platform;
- 2) A summary of **differences between countries** in terms of functions and services provided by the RECAP Platform;

3) and 4) A detailed presentation and description of **functions and services** for the different type of users and taking into account the specific use of the RECAP platform in Serbia. This is the main part of each Chapters and it is composed of:

3.3.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Farmers / Agricultural Consultant

- (F) A. Presenting Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Declaration
- (F) B. Getting assistance
- (F) C. Communicating with Inspectors
- (F) D. Communicating with Paying Agencies
- (F) E. Inserting Farmers' fields into the system

A list of main services that are offered by the RECAP Platform to users.

This example refers to Farmers / Agricultural Consultant.

As a reminder, (F) for FARMER is stand below main functions and services.

(F) **A. Presenting CAP Declaration:**

For each of the main services, a breakdown is presented.

This breakdown can be presented as a Work Flow made of different steps or as a Group of functions belonging at the same main service.

Each step and each function is presenting, inside its blue form, the corresponding option in the RECAP Platform.

For each step or each function, the different facilities of the Platform are listed.

Moreover, links are made to the corresponding option and/or bottom of the Platform.

3.3.2. *Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions*

As **Farmer / Agricultural Consultant**, you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

1. Farm Profile
2. CC Rules – Checklist
3. My Documents
4. Work diary
5. Roles
6. Reminders
7. Maps
8. BPS History
9. Help
10. Contact PA
11. Report a problem

List of the available options of the RECAP Platform.

→ Menu

Dashboard

→ Icon

For each type of user, its Dashboard is presented; and the different options that are available for this user are listed.

Each option is accessible either through the Menu or its corresponding Icon.

3. My Documents → Option of the RECAP Platform

> To upload and label documents.

Reminder about steps of functions that can be made using this option.

a) Adding a new document → Facilities available within this option

You can upload Parcels' requested documents or any other Parcels' relevant documents through **Add new**.

- 1 Click on **Add new +** ;
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document Name;
 - Description;
 - Tags;
 - Rule;
 - Tasks;
 - Parcels.

You have the possibility to tag documents and link them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels.

- 3 Click on **Visibility** to make this document always visible to the Inspectors and the Paying Agencies;
- 4 Click on **Upload media** to select the document;
- 5 Click on **Create document** to create the document.

Your document has been created.

For each option of the RECAP Platform that is available, a detailed description is provided.

It includes the different facilities available within this option for the user; as well as a detailed description of how using it.

1. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS, PROBLEM REPORTING AND TECHNICAL SUPPORT

1.1. System requirements

RECAP is designed and developed as a secure, scalable and cloud-based platform able to improve the efficiency and transparency of the Cross Compliance monitoring procedure. The RECAP platform does not require installation and configuration on the end-users' computer. It is delivered over the Internet and end-users can access them from any Internet-enabled device and location.

The mobile application is available on the Google Play store for Android phones. End-users (farmers and inspectors) who aim to download it and access all the information they may need, should have Android version 4.1 and above.

1.2. Report a problem

In order to get clear insight regarding the application functionality and greatly improve development stability over time, end-users will be able to report an issue to the development team.

The ICT specialist from each pilot country will be in charge of communication with the end-users and keep a record of any issues/ problems that may arise during the use of RECAP application in the pilot phase. In particular, they will receive via email issues/ problems identified by the end-users during the pilot implementation. These exceptional events will be evaluated based on the RECAP specifications and the final ones will be entered into a project management platform for software development TAIGA¹.

The RECAP technical team will prioritise the users' issues based on their importance and urgency. When an issue is fixed, it is updated in TAIGA as resolved and the ICT specialist gets notified by email. A final test from the ICT specialist is required in order to reassure that there were no misunderstandings from the initial issue report and the developers.

1.3. Technical support

The ICT specialist will provide support to the end-users with any technical problem that may arise with the RECAP platform throughout the pilot phase. They will be in close contact with the technical team of RECAP (DRAXIS and NOA) and their communication will be made via emails and Skype conference when necessary, always including WP4 leader in the communication.

The ICT specialist will act as the first level technical support to the end-users in the specific pilot countries. They will solve any technical issue emerging during the implementation of the pilot and only when the technical issue is of sufficient entity so that it may affect other pilot countries, or when they are not able to fix the technical issue at stake, they will raise the issue to the RECAP technical team, who will strive for a quick response in order not to delay the pilot implementation.

¹ <https://tree.taiga.io>

2. ACCESS TO THE RECAP PLATFORM

2.1. Web Interface

The RECAP Platform is accessible through the Web Interface by the following links:

- Within the RECAP Project website: <http://app.recap-h2020.eu>

The screenshot displays the RECAP web interface. At the top center is the RECAP logo. Below it is a large background image of a rural landscape with a wooden fence and green fields. Overlaid on this image is a semi-transparent green form with two columns. The left column is titled 'New User' and contains fields for Email, Password, Repeat Password, Country (with a dropdown menu showing 'United Kingdom'), Type (with a dropdown menu showing 'Farmer'), and a 'Sign up' button. The right column is titled 'Have an account?' and contains fields for Email and Password, a 'Remember me' checkbox, a 'Log in' button, and a 'Forgot password?' link. At the bottom center of the form, there is a small copyright notice: 'Copyright © RECAP 2017'.

2.2. Managing a User Account

2.2.1. Signing up in the RECAP platform

1 Within the “New User” part, fill out or select the requested information:

- Email
- Password
- Repeat Password
- Country
- Type

2 Click on **Sign up**.

3 A verification e-mail will be sent to your e-mail account: click on the **link** in order to confirm your e-mail address.

4 From now, you have a **user account created** in the RECAP platform.

Asunto: [79.143.180.124/recap/dev] Please Confirm Your E-mail Address

Hello from 79.143.180.124/recap/dev!

You're receiving this e-mail because user bcasado at 79.143.180.124/recap/dev has given yours as an e-mail address to connect their account.

To confirm this is correct, go to http://79.143.180.124/recap/dev/#!/email-confirm/MjQx:1dpaJT:udHxz7D-ReRSGNdyx_6NvwS7V0o

Thank you from 79.143.180.124/recap/dev!
79.143.180.124/recap/dev

2.2.2. Logging in

You can access to your user account through the “Have an account?” part.

1 Fill out the requested information:

- Email
- Password

2 If you want the system remember your login data, click on **Remember me**.

3 Click on **Log in**.

4 You will access the **Dashboard** that display all functions and services of the RECAP platform that are available your user type.

In case you forget your password, you can reset it. Indicate your Email and click on “**Forgot password?**”

2.2.3. Logging out

You can **logout** from your user account by:

- 1 Click on your **Avatar**;
- 2 Click on **Logout**;

2.2.4. Editing / Updating / Deleting your User Account

Once you have logged in, you can access to your personal account:

- 1 Click on your **Avatar**;
- 2 Click on **Edit Profile**;

When editing your personal account, you can update **Personal Info** and set **Preferences**.

- 1 Indicate your **First Name**;
- 2 Indicate your **Last Name**;
- 3 Select your preferences for **Language**;
- 4 Select your preferences for **Font size**;
- 5 Click on your avatar to upload a **Photo**;

Update Account

- Click on to save modifications and preferences.

When editing your personal account, you can also **delete** your personal account:

- Click on ;
- Click on **Yes** to confirm the deleting of your account.

2.2.5. Changing password

You can reset and change your password anytime you want.

- Log in** to your User Account;
- Click on **Edit Profile**;
- Indicate the requested information:
 - Old password
 - New Password
 - Confirm New Password

- Click on to save your **New Password**.

2.3. Other interfaces.

The RECAP Platform will be also accessible through the mobile app (Android) for Farmers and Inspectors.

The mobile app can be downloaded through the following link:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B5CmlXzVevnVU0dCTC1CMHEza3M>

- 1 Click on the above link through your phone;

Your phone will download the RECAP Mobile App.

- 2 Accept the installation process;

From now, the RECAP Mobile App is installed in your phone.

- 3 Log in to the RECAP Platform inserting your user account credentials:

- Email
- Password

From now, you will be able to access to the RECAP Platform trough your mobile phone and use its functions and services like you do through the Web Interface.

In addition, thanks to the Mobile App, Farmers and Inspectors will be able to upload photo through **Take Geotagged Photo.**

You will have access to the same Dashboard than the one from the Web Interface.

3. Training Guide for FARMERS / AGRICULTURAL CONSULTANTS

3.1. Brief description of users

Farmers are provided with the checklist of rules they are obliged to be compliant with according to their Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) applications. They will be guided through the rules and measures that they should take. The RECAP platform allows them to store the data, records and documents that they need to obtain, keep and present to inspectors. Using the mobile application, they will also be able to collect and store timestamped and geotaged photos from fields. Finally, they are able to communicate with the Paying Agency (PA) if they need to report exceptional circumstances.

Agricultural Consultants working for farmers can use RECAP to improve the advice to farmers in terms of the Cross Compliance procedure. They can use the spatial component to access and analyse spatial data from various sources and to access the data collected by farmers.

Moreover, Agricultural Consultants will have access to Software Developer Kit (SDK), a component of the RECAP Platform (under construction) that will let them develop their own services using design tools, libraries and communication with the database under an open approach.

3.2. Differences between countries

Regarding the user profile of Farmer / Agricultural Consultant, the RECAP Platform is offering almost the same functions and services to all the participating countries.

Dashbord's Options											
<u>Farmers / Agricultural Consultants</u>	Farm Profile	CC Rules – Checklist	My Documents	Work diary	Roles	Reminders	Maps	BPS History	Help	Contact PA	Report a problem
GREECE	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
SPAIN	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
LITHUANIA	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
UK	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
SERBIA	√	Data Management	√	√	√	√	√	OSOS History	√	√	√

There are some differences in Serbia. The RECAP Platform for Serbian Farmers presents some minor differences due to the fact that there are no Cross Compliance (CC) Rules to be fulfilled yet (at least in the frame of the Pilot); and the RECAP Platform will be used to check the compliance with organic certification requirements.

As a result, as presented in the above table, all the options will be the same for the Serbian Farmers, except two of them:

- **CC Rules – Checklist** which is replaced by **Data Management**
- **BPS History** which is replaced by **OSOS History**

These differences also generate some differences in the Work Flows and Services.

Consequently, the below sub-sections will present the common information to all Farmers / Agricultural Consultants and underlined the specific ones.

The following color code has been used within this chapter for Farmers / Agricultural Consultants:

- Common information for all Farmers / Agricultural Consultants in **Grey** steps, functions or facilities;
- Specific information for Greece, Spain, Lithuania, and U.K. in **Blue** steps, functions or facilities;
- Specific information for Serbia in **Green** steps, functions or facilities.

3.3. Functions and services - for Farmers / Agricultural Consultant

3.3.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Farmers / Agricultural Consultant

> Main services for Farmers / Agricultural Consultants checking CC Rules and presenting CAP declaration:

- (F) A. Presenting Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Declaration
- (F) B. Getting assistance
- (F) C. Communicating with Inspectors
- (F) D. Communicating with Paying Agencies
- (F) E. Inserting Farmers' fields into the system

> Specific services For Serbian Farmers / Agricultural Consultants checking the compliance with organic certification requirements:

- (SF) A. Presenting compliance with organic certification
- (SF) B. Getting assistance
- (SF) C. Communicating with Certification Bodies
- (SF) D. Communicating with Paying Agencies
- (SF) E. Inserting Farmers' fields into the system

(F) A. Presenting CAP Declaration:

(SF) A. Presenting compliance with organic certification:

A1. A1. Filling in farm details [=> FARM PROFILE]

- > Providing new data by **creating a new BPS**;
- > Updating existing data by **editing BPS data**;
- > Providing new data by **creating a new OSOS**;
- > Updating existing data by **editing OSOS data**;

A2. Checking cross compliance rules [=> CC RULES - CHECKLIST]

- > Viewing instructions to comply through each **CC Rule**;
- > Checking farmer's obligation through **Self-Assessment**;
- > Checking greening rules through **Greening Calculator**;
- > Viewing specific CC rules per parcel using **Filter by parcels**;

A2. Checking organic certification requirements [=> Data Management]

- > Viewing instructions to comply through each **Organic certification requirement**;
- > Checking farmer's obligation through **Self-Assessment**;
- > Checking greening rules through **Greening Calculator**;
- > Viewing specific O. C. requirement per parcel using **Filter by parcels**;

A3. Uploading and labelling documents [=> My Documents]

- > Uploading requested documents related to the declared parcels through **Add new**;
- > Uploading other relevant documents related to the declared parcels through **Add new**;
- > Labelling documents by tagging them with pre-defined tags and linking them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels;

(F + SF) B. Getting assistance:

B1. Getting assistance in case of Imminent Inspection [= > WORK DIARY]

> Keeping the Records on input / output / work diary.

B2. Getting assistance on Calendar Important Dates to be reminded [= > REMINDERS]

> Indicating Important Dates (Date of Event / Date to be reminded) though **Add New Reminder**;
> Viewing Inspector's Notification for events that have been scheduled;

B3. Customizing assistance [= > REMINDERS]

> Creating own customized reminders though **Add New Reminder**;
> Displaying your Reminders either as a calendar or as a list though **View as Calendar / View as List**;

B4. Granting access to other users [= > ROLES]

> Including additional users and defining role and access level (e.g. for transferring ownership of Farmers' account to a consultant or a farm staff) through **Add**.

B5. Accessing prior BPS claim [= > BPS History]

> Accessing prior BPS and their corresponding information by selecting the **year (e.g. 2016)**;

B5. Accessing prior OSOS claim [= > OSOS History]

> Accessing prior OSOS and their corresponding information by selecting the **year (e.g. 2016)**;

B6. Accessing helping documents from Paying Agency [= > Help]

> Searching documents through **Search My Documents**;
> Specifying searches with labels through **Advanced Search**;

(F) C. Communicating with Inspectors:

(SF) C. Communicating with Certification Bodies:

C1. C1. Giving access to farmers' information [=> CC RULES – CHECKLIST / DATA MANAGEMENT]

> Giving visibility to documents, work diary and input /output table through **Make me visible**;

C2. Checking state of progress of completion of rules [=> CC RULES - CHECKLIST]

> Viewing the summary of obligations (must do and missing documents) through **Self-Assessment**;
> Viewing the inspection results grouped per CC rule with any supportive documents uploaded by inspectors through **Inspector Assessment (I)** and by **selecting the Rule (e.g. GAEC 1)**;

C2. Checking state of progress of completion of organic requirements [=>DATA MANAGEMENT]

> Viewing the summary of obligations (must do and missing documents) through **Self-Assessment**;
> Viewing the certification bodies' results grouped per O. C. requirement with any supportive documents uploaded by certification bodies by **selecting the O. C. requirement (e.g. Organic Plant Production)**;

C3. Exchanging directly with Inspectors [=> mailing box]

> Being contacted by Inspectors that will send a message to your email;

C3. Exchanging directly with Certification Bodies [=> mailing box]

> Being contacted by Certification Bodies that will send a message to your email;

(F+ SF) D. Communicating with Paying Agencies:

D1. D1. Giving access to farmers' information [=> CC RULES - CHECKLIST / DATA MANAGEMENT]

> Giving visibility to documents, work diary and input /output table through **Make me visible**;

D2. Exchanging directly with PAs [=> Contact PA]

> Asking specific questions to PAs;
> Viewing exchanges with PAs.

(F) E. Inserting Farmers' fields into the system

E1. Accessing and inserting parcel information [=> MAPS]

> Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information through **Search parcels / Parcel List / Select parcel**;
> Inserting / Deleting Farmers' fields through **Draw parcel**.

3.3.2. Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions

As **Farmer / Agricultural Consultant**, you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

1. Farm Profile
2. **CC Rules – Checklist**
3. My Documents
4. Work diary
5. Roles
6. Reminders
7. Maps
8. **BPS History**
9. Help
10. Contact PA
11. Report a problem

In the Serbian Dashboard, the only differences will be the two following options:

2. **Data Management**
8. **OSOS History**

1. Farm Profile

> To fill in farm details.

a) Creating a new BPS claim

You can provide new data by creating a new BPS.

1 Click on ;

2 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Farmer's personal name;
- Farmer's personal last name;
- Year of Application.

3 Click on .

You have created a new BPS.

4 Continue with the process, filling out or selecting the requested information for each Step of the process; and clicking on

.

Depending on your country, the process is composed of a different number of Steps (including BPS and Questionnaire):

- **Greece:** 4 Steps in total;
- **Spain:** 4 Steps in total;
- **Lithuania:** 17 Steps in total;
- **UK:** 11 Steps in total.

Line	Parcel name	Parcel ID	Area	Municipality code	Slope	Ratio admissibility pasture	Ratio irrigated area	Cap Use	Add
1 of 1									

Line	Parcel name	Parcel ID	Area	Municipality code	Slope	Ratio admissibility pasture	Ratio irrigated area	Cap Use	Add
1	field1001	1001	1730.20	123	1	0.50	1.50	VINEYARD	Add Geometry Edit Delete Add cap declaration
1 of 1									

At the end of the process, you will reach the last step which is called **Questionnaire**.

For each question:

- 1 Put a mark in the box if the reply is **Yes**;
- 2 Click on to select the Parcels which are relevant for the corresponding question;
- 3 Select the parcels that are concerned by putting a mark in the box.
- 4 Click on .

Once you will have answer to all questions, you will have finalized the process. You can

b) Editing BPS data

You can **edit BPS data** and update existing information anytime you want up until the date of submission:

- 1 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Farmer's personal name;
 - Farmer's personal last name;
 - Year of Application.
- 2 Click on .

You will access to all the information uploaded for this Farmer and the selected year of application.

You will have the possibility to modify / update the information of the selected BPS.

1. Farm Profile (for Serbian Case)

> To fill in farm details.

a) Creating a new OSOS claim

You can provide new data by **creating a new OSOS**.

1 Click on ;

2 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Farmer's personal name;
- Farmer's personal last name;
- Farmer's unique registration number of the citizen;
- Contact person for organic farming:
- Farmer's address:
- Farmer's town:
- Farmer's municipality:
- Postal code of residence:
- Farmer's personal tax number:
- Farmer's telephone:
- Farmer's personal fax number:
- Farmer's farm identification number:
- Farmer's personal web site:
- Year of Application.

3 Click on .

You have created a new OSOS.

4 Continue with the process, filling out or selecting the requested information for each Step of the process; and clicking on

The process is composed of a 12 Steps (including the OSOS one).

b) Editing OSOS data

You can **edit OSOS data** and update existing information anytime you want:

1 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Farmer's personal name;
- Farmer's personal last name;
- Farmer's unique registration number of the citizen;
- Contact person for organic farming:
- Farmer's address:
- Farmer's town:
- Farmer's municipality:
- Postal code of residence:
- Farmer's personal tax number:
- Farmer's telephone:
- Farmer's personal fax number:
- Farmer's farm identification number:
- Farmer's personal web site:
- Year of Application.

2 Click on **Next** :

You will access to all the information uploaded for this Farmer and the selected year of application.

You will have the possibility to modify / update the information of the selected OSOS.

2. CC Rules – Checklist

- > To check cross compliance rules.
- > To give access to farmers' information.
- > To check progress of complying with relevant rules.

a) CC Rule

Depending on your inputs, the system decides which Cross Compliance (CC) rules apply to your fields and you will see a list of all relevant rules that you need to be compliant with.

The list that will be displayed in your screen will be similar to the following one depending on your inputs:

For each **CC Rule**, you can view instructions to comply it.

- 1 Click on a **CC Rule**;

You will get a description of the rule, a summary of obligations / tasks (must do and must not do); as well as the possibility to (i) post comment, (ii) upload/view documents, (iii) upload/view images and (iv) indicate state of tasks.

For posting a comment:

- 1 Click on ;

The following window will appear.

2 Write your comment;

3 Click on

Your comment has been posted and the number of message associated to the Icon has incremented to 1 more message.

From now, this message can be seen by you and the Inspector by clicking on the Icon.

For uploading documents or images:

1 Click on the left side of the documents icon ;

2 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Document name;
- Description ;
- Tags ;
- Parcels ;

3 Click on to select the document / image;

4 Click on to upload the document / image.

Your document / image has been uploaded.

For viewing documents or images:

1 Click on the right side of the documents icon ;

A window will appear, displaying the uploaded documents / images.

2 Click on the document / image of your interest;

Information about the selected document / image will appear.

3 Click on:

- to download it;
- to modify information related to it;
- to delete it.

For indicating the state of tasks:

1 Click on the red box .

Once all the tasks will be marked as checked:

- the compliance state of the rule will change from

 ;

- the aspect of the CC rule (in the dashboard of the CC Rules – Checklist) will also change from orange

.

b) Self-Assessment

You can check farmer’s obligation through **Self-Assessment** .

1 Click on ;

You will get a summary of all the requested tasks and documents that are still necessary.

Task	Met	Condition	Documents	Start date	Deadline	CCRule	Inspector compliance	Self compliance
Respect 3 meters without tilling	Yes	Affected plots			15-Jan-15-Jan-15-Apr	GAEC 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Spread manure and (or) slurry in water protection zones	No					GAEC 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Respect 5 meters untreated	Yes	Affected plots		15-Jun		GAEC 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
None	Yes		Annotation in the logbook of phyto sanitary treatments Organic Residues in the logbooks of waste management			GAEC 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Have Authorization by the hydrographic Confederation or the Irrigation Community	Yes		Authorization by the hydrographic Confederation or the Irrigation Community			GAEC 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
None	Yes					GAEC 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
None	Yes					GAEC 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Store hazardous materials in a way which allows to avoid their direct or indirect access to the groundwater; hazardous materials must be sealed, their packaging should not have any cracks or other mechanical damage and must be stored in a sealed case which prevents from getting dangerous substances into the ground.	Yes					GAEC 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Release the effluents contaminated with hazardous substances into groundwater.	No					GAEC 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Free from	Yes	Slope less than 15%				GAEC 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

c) Self-Assessment (S) / Inspector Assessment (I)

Back to the CC Rules – Checklist’s Dashboard, you can check the state of progress of completion of rules for both, self-assessment and inspector assessment:

- For Self-Assessment, click on **(S)** to view the Farmer’s compliance grouped per CC rule:

- For Inspector Assessment click on **(I)** to view the Inspection results grouped per CC rule:

You will also have access to any supportive documents or images uploaded by inspectors by selecting the Rule (e.g. GAEC 1).

d) Greening Calculator

You can check greening rules through **Greening Calculator**

- 1 Click on Greening Calculator ;

You will get the result about the declared sub parcels and their corresponding greening calculation. They will be based on the data entered already into the system.

Greening Calculator for parcels	
Total area: 539368.3569685259	
Min crop area is less than 5% of total area. Crop Code that fails condition is: 5	
Crop Name	Values
5	0.00 %
15	0.77 %

e) Filtering by parcels

You can view the CC rules applied to a specific parcel by using the Filter to select any specific parcel:

f) Make me visible

You can give access to your information to Inspectors and Paying Agencies through **Make me visible**.

- 1 Click on **Make me visible**

The following window will appear:

Making documents visible

Are you sure you want to make your documents and work-diary visible to inspector?

- 2 Click on **Yes** to accept information sharing with the inspector and Paying Agencies.

From now, your information (documents, work diary and input /output table) will be visible to the Inspectors and Paying Agencies.

In case you want to close your information to the Inspectors and Paying Agencies:

- 1 Click on **Make me invisible** and then, on **Yes**

Your information (documents, work diary and input /output table) will not be any more visible to the Inspectors and Paying Agencies.

2. Data Management

- > To check organic certification requirements.
- > To give access to farmers' information.
- > To check progress of complying with relevant requirements.

a) Organic certification requirement

Depending on your inputs, the system decides which Organic Certification requirement apply to your fields and you will see a list of all relevant requirements that you need to be compliant with.

The list that will be displayed in your screen will be similar to the following one depending on your inputs:

For each **Organic certification requirement**, you can view instructions to comply it.

- 1 Click on an **Organic certification requirement**;

You will get a description of the requirement; as well as the possibility to (i) post comment, (ii) upload/view documents, and (iii) upload/view images.

For posting a comment:

- 1 Click on ;

The following window will appear.

Author	Comment
	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px; min-height: 100px;"> <p>Post a new comment</p> </div> <div style="text-align: right; margin-top: 10px;"> <input type="button" value="Post comment"/> </div>

1 of 1

2 Write your comment;

3 Click on: .

Your comment has been posted and the number of message associated to the Icon has incremented to 1 more message.

From now, this message can be seen by you and the Certification Body by clicking on the Icon.

For uploading documents or images:

- 1 Click on the left side of the documents icon ;
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document name;
 - Description ;
 - Tags ;
 - Parcels ;

3 Click on to select the document / image;

4 Click on to upload the document / image.

Your document / image has been uploaded.

For viewing documents or images:

- 1 Click on the right side of the documents icon ;

A window will appear, displaying the uploaded documents / images.

- 2 Click on the document / image of your interest;

Information about the selected document / image will appear.

3 Click on:

- to download it;
- to modify information related to it;
- to delete it.

b) Self-Assessment

Back to the Data Management’s Dashboard, you can check farmer’s obligation regarding completion of Organic certification requirement through **Self-Assessment**.

1 Click on **Self Assessment** ;

You will get a summary of all the requested tasks and documents that are still necessary.

Misc	Condition	Document	Start date	Deadline	CCU/UE	Inspector compliance	Self compliance
Yes					Organic Plant Production	✗	✗
Yes					Group Of Producers for Plant	✗	✗
Yes					Mushroom Production	✗	✗
Yes					Wild Plants	✗	✗
Yes					Apiculture	✗	✗
Yes					Group Of Producers for Apiculture	✗	✗
Yes					Animal Production	✗	✗
Yes					Group Of Producers for Animal	✗	✗
Yes					Processing	✗	✗
Yes					Trade	✗	✗

c) Greening Calculator

You can check greening rules through **Greening Calculator**

1 Click on **Greening Calculator** ;

You will get the result about the declared sub parcels and their corresponding greening calculation. They will be based on the data entered already into the system.

Crop Name	Values
5	0.00 %
15	0.77 %

d) Filtering by parcels

You can view the O. C. requirement applied to a specific parcel by using the Filter to select any specific parcel:

e) Make me visible

You can give access to your information to Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies through **Make me visible**.

- 1 Click on **Make me visible**

The following window will appear:

Making documents visible

Are you sure you want to make your documents and work-diary visible to inspector?

- 2 Click on **Yes** to accept information sharing with the Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies.

From now, your information (documents, work diary and input /output table) will be visible to the Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies.

In case you want to close your information to the Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies:

- 1 Click on **Make me invisible** and then, on **Yes**

Your information (documents, work diary and input /output table) will not be any more visible to the Certification Bodies and Paying Agencies.

3. My Documents

> *To upload and label documents.*

a) Adding a new document

You can upload Parcels' requested documents or any other Parcels' relevant documents through **Add new**.

- 1 Click on
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document Name;
 - Description;
 - Tags;
 - Rule;
 - Tasks;
 - Parcels.

You have the possibility to tag documents and link them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels.

- 3 Click on to make this document always visible to the Inspectors and the Paying Agencies;
- 4 Click on to select the document;
- 5 Click on to create the document.

Your document has been created.

b) Labelling documents

You can tag documents with a pre-defined list of categories and link them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels anytime you want.

- 1 Click on the document you want to tag or link to something;
- 2 Click on ;
- 3 Indicate / Modify the information you want to connect to this document by selecting the below information:

- Tags;
- Rule;
- Tasks;
- Parcels.

4 Click on to save modifications.

The document is now tagged and linked according to the indicated information.

4. Work diary

> To get assistance in case of Imminent Inspection.

a) Recording inputs / outputs / work diary

You can get assistance in case of imminent inspection through **Work diary**, by having detailed tracking of all inputs and outputs.

You will be able to record and keep your inputs / output / work diary into your **Work diary**.

1 Click on ;

2 Fill out / Select the requested information;

3 Click on ;

You have saved your inputs / output / work diary.

5. Roles

> *To grant access to other users.*

a) Including additional users

You can include additional users and define role and access level for users (e.g. for transferring rights of Farmers' account to a consultant or a member of farm staff) through **Add**.

1 Click on **Add**

2 Fill out / Select the requested information;

- Email;
- Role Name;
- Role.

3 Click on **Save** ;

A new user has been created within your account according to the indicated Role.

The status of this user will remain **Pending** until it will accept the role.

This user will receive the following email from the RECAP Platform in order to let it access to the Platform, create an account and accept or reject the Role.

b) Defining / Modifying roles

You can define or modify role and access level of your additional users any time you want.

1 Click on **Edit** ;

The profile of the selected user will be displayed.

#	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	Role Name	Role	Status	
1	Not registered	Not registered	testing@gmail.com	Agricultural advisor	Read	Pending	Edit

2 Indicate / Modify the following information:

- Role Name;
- Role.

3 Click on to save the new role and access level of this user.

The role and access level for this user have been updated.

6. Reminders

- > To get assistance on Calendar Important Dates to be reminded.
- > To customize assistance.
- > To get assistance on the Remote Sensing Process.

a) Adding a New Reminder

You can indicate Key Dates (Date of Event / Date to be reminded) or create own customized reminders though **Add New Reminder**.

You can indicate Key Dates (Date of Event / Date to be reminded) though **Add New Reminder**.

- 1 Click on ;
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information;
 - Date of the Event;
 - How much before to be reminded;
 - Description;
 - Cell undefined 1 (e.g. time);
 - Cell undefined 2 (e.g. duration).
- 3 Click on to save data.

Your reminder has been created.

b) Viewing Inspector's Notification for events that have been scheduled

In addition to your Reminders, you can see notifications for events that have been scheduled by the Inspectors.

c) Displaying your Reminders

You can view all your Reminders displaying them either in a calendar view or as a list.

For displaying them as a List, click on ;

For displaying them as a Calendar, click on .

7. Maps

> To access and insert parcel information.

a) Visualizing maps and accessing parcel information

The system will automatically load your parcels when getting into **Maps**.

You can view maps and information of a specific parcel:

- 1 Click on **Parcel List** ;
- 2 Click on to view parcel information;

You can also do it through **Search parcels**.

- 1 Indicate the parcel ID in **Search parcel**;

Or even though the **Select parcel** option:

- 1 Click on to activate it;
- 2 Click on the parcel of interest.

You will view the maps and information of the selected parcel as displayed here:

- The parcel information is displayed on the right side of the window;

- The maps can be visualized with different layers.

- 1 Click on ;

A new section will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different layers that are available.

- 2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;

- 3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

b) Inserting / Deleting yours fields into the system

You can create, update or delete the geometry of your parcels anytime you want.

For creating geometry:

You can create a geometry by drawing the shape over the map through **Draw parcel**;

- 1 Click on to activate **Draw Parcel**;
- 2 Draw the shape of your parcel over the map with the blue line;

Once the shape will be defined, the following window will open:

- 3 From the list of parcels, select the one corresponding to the shape you drawn;

Once the parcel will be selected, the red mark will move to a green one;

- 4 Click on ;

You have successfully created your parcel. From now, the information of your parcel is connected to this geometry.

For deleting geometry:

- 1 Click on to activate the delete option;
- 2 Select the parcel you want to delete its geometry;

The following window will appear:

- 3 Click on to confirm the deletion;

You have successfully removed the geometry of your parcel. From now, the information of your parcel is no longer connected to any geometry.

8. BPS History

> To access prior BPS.

a) Accessing prior BPS

You can access to your prior BPS and their corresponding information by selecting the **year (e.g. 2016)**;

- 1 Click on the **BPS year**;

You will access to all the information related to the selected BPS.

8. OSOS History

> To access prior OSOS

a) Accessing prior OSOS

You can access to your prior OSOS and their corresponding information by selecting the **year (e.g. 2016)**;

- 1 Click on the **OSOS year**;

You will access to all the information related to the selected OSOS.

9. Help

> To access helping documents from Paying Agency.

a) Searching My Documents

You can perform searches with key words.

1 Enter your key words in **Search My Documents**;

2 Click on enter;

The result of your search will be displayed.

b) Advanced Search

You can perform specific searches with labels.

1 Click on **Advanced Search** ;

New functionalities will appear.

2 Click on **Types** and select the ones you want putting a mark ;

The criteria of your search will be applied and the corresponding documents will be displayed.

10. Contact PA

> To exchange directly with Paying Agencies.

a) Asking specific question

You can directly contact your Paying Agency. The following window will appear when getting into **Contact PA**.

- 1 Fill out the requested information:
 - Title of your message;
 - Content of your message.

- 2 Click on **Send**.

Your message has been sent to your Paying Agency.

b) Viewing exchanges

You can view answers to your questions and access to the history of your communication with PA.

This information will appear on the top of the window when entering the **Contact PA** screen.

11. Report a problem

Report a problem

> To inform about technical issues of the RECAP Platform.

a) Reporting a problem

You can report a problem any time you want. The following window will appear when getting into **Report a problem**.

1 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Select problem type;
- Write a description of the problem;

2 You have the option to upload a picture of the problem (not mandatory). To do it, click on **upload media** and select the file;

3 Click on **Report a problem**.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Report a problem" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form contains the following elements:

- A dropdown menu labeled "Select problem type:" with "System error" selected.
- A text area labeled "Write a description of the problem:".
- An optional section labeled "Upload a picture of a problem (optional):" containing two buttons: "upload media" and "Report a problem".

Your reporting problem has been sent.

4. Training Guide for INSPECTORS / CERTIFICATION BODIES

4.1. Brief description of users

Inspectors are able to access the data and material related to the farm to be inspected in the case of remote inspection or to download any data needed for On-The-Spot-Checks (OTSC) in the RECAP mobile/tablet application environment. They are provided with a checklist of rules specific to the farm that will guide them through the inspection process.

Serbian Certification Bodies are also able to access the data and material related to the farm. They will use the RECAP Platform as Data Management Tool for monitoring farmer’s compliance with organic certification requirement.

4.2. Differences between countries

Regarding the user profile of Inspectors, the RECAP Platform is offering the same functions and services to most of the participating countries.

Dashbord's Options							
<u>Inspectors</u>	Inspection Forms	Inspections	Scheduler	My Documents	Farmer's Work diary	Maps	Inspection History
GREECE	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
SPAIN	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
LITHUANIA	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
UK	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

- When inspecting a farmer.
- When visibility is given by farmer.

In Serbia, the Dashboard’s Options are different. This is due to the fact that the certification body selects a farmer for monitoring farmer’s compliance with organic certification requirements in the frame of the Serbian Pilot.

Dashbord's Options												
<u>Certification Bodies</u>	Farmers	My Documents	Messages	Maps	OSOS Forms	Farmers	Data Management	My Documents	User Documents	Messages	Work diary	Maps
SERBIA	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

- When monitoring farmer's compliance with organic certification requ

4.3. Functions and services - for Inspectors

4.3.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Inspectors

- (I) A. Inspecting BPS Declaration
- (I) B. Accessing the Farmer's information
- (I) C. Communicating with Farmers

(I) A. Inspecting BPS Declaration:

A1. Selecting Farmer and BPS year for inspection [=> INSPECTIONS]

- > Accessing Farmers' data (with farmer's permission) by **Open inspection Forms**;
- > Asking farmer's permission to view his documents through **Request BPS Visibility**;

A2. Making the inspection and completing the inspection form [=> INSPECTION FORMS]

- > Viewing farmers CC rules checklist (if farmers give his access to make his info visible) through **CC Rules Checklist**;
- > Inspecting each CC Rules and indicating the corresponding status by **Select status from the list**;
- > Creating and visualizing inspection events through **Schedule Inspection**;
- > Viewing the activities performed in the platform through **Log History**;
- > Submitting the final decision to the RECAP platform and sending a reporting email to the Farmer and the Paying Agencies through **Submit Final Decision**.

A3. Scheduling Inspection for a Farmer [=> SCHEDULER]

- > Scheduling Inspection, sending an email to the Farmer and displaying a notification within the farmer's app through **Send Email**;
- > Viewing the Farmer's scheduled events (if the access is allowed by the farmer);

A4. Submitting Final Decision [=> INSPECTION FORMS]

- > Submitting the final decision to the RECAP platform and sending a reporting email to the Farmer and the Paying Agencies through **Submit Final Decision**.

(I) **B. Accessing the Farmer's information**

<p>B1. Viewing / Searching Farmer's documents</p> Inspection History			
--	---	--	---

B1. Viewing / Searching Farmer's documents (if it is allowed by the Farmer) [= > MY DOCUMENTS]

- > Searching documents in the system through **Search My Documents**;
- > Specifying searches with labels through **Advanced Search**;

B2. Viewing Farmer's Work Diary (if it is allowed by the Farmer) [= > WORK DIARY]

- > Viewing Farmer's Work Diary

B3. Accessing the spatial information and the farm-related data [= > MAPS]

- > Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information needed for the inspection process through **Search parcels / Parcel List / Select parcel**;

B4. Accessing the Farmer's List of BPS years [= > Inspection History]

- > Accessing information from prior inspections by selecting the corresponding **year** (e.g. 2016);

(I) **C. Communicating with Farmers**

C1. Asking permission to access Farmer's information [=> INSPECTIONS]

> Asking for Farmer's permission to access to its information (documents, work diary and inputs/outputs tables) through **Request BPS Visibility**;

C2. Exchanging directly with Farmers [=> SCHEDULER]

> Sending an email to the Farmer through **Send email**;

C3. Informing Farmers about Final Decision [=> INSPECTION FORMS]

> Sending a reporting email to the Farmer and the Paying Agencies through **Submit Final Decision**.

C4. Providing Farmers with Documents [=> MY DOCUMENTS]

> Uploading documents (tagging them and linking them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels) regarding the inspection through **Add new**;

4.3.2. Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions

As **Inspector**, in Greece, Spain, Lithuania and U.K., you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

1. Inspections

- 1.1. Inspection Forms
- 1.2. Inspections
- 1.3. Scheduler
- 1.4. My Documents
- 1.5. Farmer's Work diary
- 1.6. Maps
- 1.7. Inspection History

1. Inspections

- > To select Farmer and BPS year for inspection.
- > To ask permission to access Farmer's information.

a) Opening / Closing inspection Forms

You can have access to the Farmers' data by opening inspection forms.

- 1 Click on **Open inspection Forms** ;

You will have access to the complete information from the Farmer only if it would have previously made it visible.

In case this Farmer did not already make its data visible, you can send it a request:

- 1 Click on **Request BPS Visibility** ;

A request has been sent to this Farmer.

In case this Farmer already made its data visible, you will not have the option **Request BPS Visibility** available anymore; and have access to the **Farmer's Work diary**.

1.1. Inspection Forms

- > To make the inspection and complete the inspection form.
- > To submit Final Decision
- > To inform Farmers and PAs about Final Decision

a) Processing inspections of CAP declaration

You will access to **Step 1** of the inspection process and see the results for the CC Rules as display in the following window:

You can view farmers CC rules checklist (if farmers give his access to make his info visible) through **CC Rules Checklist**;

1 Click on **CCRules Checklist** ;

CC Rules	Select status from the list
GAEC 1: Establishment of buffer strips along watercourses	PENDING
GAEC 2: Water abstraction	PENDING
GAEC 3: Groundwater	PENDING
GAEC 4: Providing minimum soil cover	PENDING
GAEC 5: Minimising soil erosion	PENDING
GAEC 6: Maintaining the level of organic matter in soil	PENDING
GAEC 7: Landscapes	PENDING
SMR 1: Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ)	PENDING
SMR 2: Wild birds	PENDING
SMR 3: Habitats and species	PENDING
SMR 10: Plant Protection Products (PPP)	PENDING
None: None	PENDING

CC Rules	Status
-GAEC 1- Establishment of buffer strips along watercourses	Not checked
-GAEC 2- Water abstraction	Not checked
-GAEC 3- Groundwater	Not checked
-GAEC 5- Minimising soil erosion	Not checked
-GAEC 6- Maintaining the level of organic matter in soil	Not checked
-GAEC 7- Landscapes	Not checked
-SMR 1- Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ)	Not checked
-SMR 2- Wild birds	Not checked
-SMR 10- Plant Protection Products (PPP)	Not checked

You can inspect each CC Rules and indicating the corresponding status by **Select status from the list**;

CC Rules	Select status from the list
GAEC 1: Establishment of buffer strips along watercourses	CHECKED
GAEC 3: Groundwater	CHECKED
SMR 10: Plant Protection Products (PPP)	BREACH DETECTED
None: None	PENDING

You can create and visualize inspection events through **Schedule Inspection**;

- 1 Click on [Schedule Inspection](#) ;

You can view the activities performed in the platform through **Log History**;

- 1 Click on [Log History](#) ;

You can submit the final decision to the RECAP platform and send a reporting email to the Farmer and the Paying Agencies through **Submit Final Decision**.

- 1 Click on [Submit Final Decision](#) ;

1.3. Scheduler

- > To schedule Inspection for a Farmer
- > To view the Farmer's scheduled events
- > To exchange directly with Farmers.

a) Sending an email to Farmer

You can schedule an Inspection or directly exchange with the Farmer, sending an email to the Farmer and displaying a notification within the farmer's app through **Send Email**;

- 1 Click on
- 2 Fill out the requested information:
 - Subject of your message;
 - Content of your message.
- 3 Click on **Send**.

Your message has been sent to the Farmer.

Subject

Message

b) Viewing the Farmer's scheduled events

You can also view the Farmer's scheduled events (if the access is allowed by the farmer) when entering to the **Scheduler**.

1.4. My Documents

- > To view / search Farmer's documents (if it is allowed by the Farmer)
- > To provide Farmers with Documents

a) Viewing / Searching Farmer's documents

You can access to Farmer's document into **My documents**.

You can perform searches with key words.

1 Enter your key words in **Search My Documents**;

2 Press enter.

The result of your search will be displayed.

b) Advanced Search

You can perform specific searches with labels.

1 Click on **Advanced Search** ;

New functionalities will appear.

For each of the following categories, you will be able to specify your searches:

- Rules
- Tasks
- Tags
- Parcels
- Types

2 Click on each one and select the ones you want putting a mark ;

The criteria of your search will be applied and the corresponding documents will be displayed.

c) Adding a new document

You can provide Farmers with documents uploading them through **Add new**.

- 1 Click on
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document Name;
 - Description;
 - Tags;
 - Rule;
 - Tasks;
 - Parcels.

You have the possibility to tag documents and link them to Rules, Tasks and/or Parcels.

- 3 Click on to make this document always visible to the Inspectors and the Paying Agencies;
- 4 Click on to select the document;
- 5 Click on to create the document.

Your document has been created.

d) Labelling documents

You can tag anytime you want.

- 1 Click on the document you want to tag;
- 2 Click on ;
- 3 Indicate / Modify the tags you want to connect to this document by putting / removing them;
- 4 Click on to save modifications.

The document is now tagged according to the indicated information.

1.5. Farmer's Work diary

> To view Farmer's Work Diary (if it is allowed by the Farmer)

a) Viewing Farmer's Work Diary

You will have access to the complete information registered in the Farmer's Work Diary.

You will have access to it only if it has previously been made visible by the farmer.

In case the Farmer did not already make their data visible, you can send the farmer a request (see "1. Inspections") through the option **Request BPS Visibility**.

1.6. Maps

> To access to the spatial information and the farm-related data

a) Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information

The system will automatically load the Farmer's parcels when getting into **Maps**.

You can view maps and information of a specific parcel:

- 1 Click on **Parcel List** ;
- 2 Click on to view the Parcel of interest;

You can also do it through **Search parcels**.

- 1 Indicate the parcel ID in **Search parcel**;

Or even though the **Select parcel** option:

- 1 Click on to activate it;
- 2 Click on the parcel of interest.

You will view the maps and information of the selected parcel as displayed here:

- The parcel information is displayed on the right side of the window;

- The maps can be visualized with different layers.

1 Click on ;

A new part will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different Layers that are available.

2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;

3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

b) Suggesting Parcel geometry

You can suggest geometry to the Farmer.

For creating geometry:

You can create geometry by drawing the shape over the map through **Draw parcel**;

1 Click on to activate **Draw Parcel**;

2 Draw the shape of your parcel over the map with the blue dotted line;

Once the shape will be defined, the following window will open:

3 Click on to confirm the creation of the suggested geometry;

You have successfully suggested the geometry.

1.7. Inspection History

> To access to prior BPS years of the Farmer

a) Accessing prior Farmer's BPS

You can access to prior BPS years of the Farmer and their corresponding information by selecting the **year** (e.g. 2016);

- 1 Click on the **BPS year**;

You will access to all the information related to the selected BPS.

4.4. Functions and services - for Serbian Certification Bodies

In Serbia, since the RECAP Platform will be used for checking the compliance with organic certification requirements instead of checking CC Rules and presenting CAP declaration, the monitoring of farmer's compliance with organic certification requirement will be made by **Certification Bodies**.

Indeed, instead of the Services and Functions described in the prior section 4.3, the RECAP Platform is offering different Services and Functions to Serbian Certification Bodies as described in this section.

4.4.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Serbian Certification Bodies

- (SCB) A. Monitoring Farmer's compliance
- (SCB) B. Communicating with Farmers and accessing their information (if it is allowed by the Farmer)
- (SCB) C. Getting assistance

(SCB) A. Monitoring Farmer's compliance:

A1. Selecting Farmer and OSOS year for monitoring compliance [=> Farmers]

- > Accessing Farmers' data (with farmer's permission) by **View OSOS History**;
- > Viewing the List of OSOS for a Farmer (with farmer's permission) by selecting the corresponding **OSOS year (e.g. 2016)**.

A2. Accessing farm details (with farmer's permission) [=> OSOS FORM]

- > Accessing existing / available data by **Edit OSOS data**.

A2. Checking organic certification requirements [=> Data Management]

- > Viewing instructions to comply through each **Organic certification requirement**;
- > Checking farmer's obligation through **Self-Assessment**;
- > Checking greening rules through **Greening Calculator**;
- > Viewing specific O. C. requirement per parcel using **Filter by parcels**;
- > Providing Farmer's with documents/images related to O. C. requirements through **Other documents**;

(SCB) B. Communicating with Farmers and accessing their information (if it is allowed by the Farmer)

B1. Viewing Farmer's messages and exchanging directly with Farmers [=> MESSAGES]

- > Accessing a specific Farmer's messages through **View Messages**;
- > Sending a message to a specific Farmer through **View Messages**;
- > Asking for Farmer's permission to access to its information (documents, work diary and inputs/outputs tables) through **Send**;

B2. Viewing / Searching Farmer's documents (if it is allowed by the Farmer) [=> USER DOCUMENTS]

- > Searching Farmer's documents in the system through **Search My Documents**;
- > Specifying searches with labels through **Advanced Search**;

B3. Viewing Farmer's Work Diary (if it is allowed by the Farmer) [=> WORK DIARY]

- > Viewing Farmer's Work Diary

B4. Accessing Farmer's spatial information and the farm-related data (if it is allowed by the Farmer) [=> Remote Sensing Results]

- > Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information needed for the monitoring process through **Search parcels / Parcel List / Select parcel**;

B5. Providing Farmers with documents [=> MY DOCUMENTS]

- > Uploading and tagging documents regarding the monitoring through **Add new / Edit media**;

(SCB) C. Getting assistance

B1. Searching documents Remote Sensing Results	
---	---

B1. Searching documents [=> MY DOCUMENTS]

- > Searching documents in the system through **Search My Documents**;
- > Specifying searches with labels through **Advanced Search**;

B2. Accessing the spatial information [=> Remote Sensing Results]

- > Visualizing maps and bounding's information through **Remote Sensing Results**;

4.4.2. Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions

As Serbian **Certification Body**, you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

1. Farmers
2. My Documents
3. Messages
4. Remote Sensing Results

- 1.1. OSOS Forms
- 1.2. Farmers
- 1.2. Data Management
- 1.4. My Documents
- 1.3. User Documents
- 1.6. Messages
- 1.4. Work Diary
- 1.7. Remote Sensing Results

1. Farmers

> To select Farmer and OSOS year for monitoring compliance.

a) Viewing OSOS History / Closing Farmer Forms

You can have access to the Farmers' data by viewing OSOS history.

- 1 Click on [View OSOS History](#) ;
- 2 Click on the **OSOS year** of interest (e.g. 2017).

You will have access to the complete information from the Farmer and the selected OSOS year (only if the Farmer has previously made its information visible through **Make me visible**).

#	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	Actions
1	Petar	Petrovic	farmer_sr@example.com	Close OSOS Form View OSOS History
2	Milan	Steganovic	polen20@mts.rs	View OSOS History
3			organicpivice@gmail.com	View OSOS History
4			rodicdmistar@yahoo.com	View OSOS History
5	Zeljko	Dimtric	drzeek@gmail.com	View OSOS History
6			goran.rodic@gmail.com	View OSOS History
7	Branislav	Andelic	bandelic@plavinci.rs	View OSOS History
8	Dmitar	Rodic	goran.rodic@gmail.com	View OSOS History
9			ekoadult@gmail.com	View OSOS History
10	aaa	aaa	proba_sr@example.com	View OSOS History

2. My Documents

- > To search documents.
- > To provide Farmers with documents.

a) Searching documents

You can perform searches with key words within auxiliary materials you have uploaded.

1 Enter your key words in **Search My Documents**;

2 Click on Enter.

The result of your search will be displayed.

b) Advanced Search

You can perform specific searches with labels.

1 Click on **Advanced Search** ;

New functionalities will appear.

2 Click on **Types** and select the ones you want putting a mark ;

The result of your search will be displayed.

c) Adding a new document

You can upload documents through **Add new**.

- 1 Click on
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document Name;
 - Description;
 - Tags.

You have the possibility to **tag** documents putting marks in the relevant tags.

- 3 Click on to select the document;
- 4 Click on to create the document.

Your document has been created.

d) Labelling documents

You can tag documents anytime you want.

- 1 Click on the document you want to tag;
- 2 Click on ;
- 3 Indicate / Modify the tags you want to connect to this document by adding / removing them;
- 4 Click on to save modifications.

The document is now tagged according to the indicated information.

3. Messages

> To view Farmer's messages and exchange directly with Farmers

a) Viewing Farmer's messages

You can access the entire Farmer's messages (the ones the Farmer sent to the Paying Agency and the ones you sent to the Farmer) through **View Messages**.

From the list of users:

- 1 Click on **View Messages** for the farmer of interest;

Information will appear on the top of the window.

a) Sending messages to farmers

You can send a message to a farmer through **View Messages** (on the bottom of the window).

- 1 Fill out the requested information:
 - Title of your message;
 - Content of your message.

You can attach a document to your message.

- 2 Click on **Upload Media** and select the document you want to join;
- 2 Click on **Send**.

Your message has been sent to the selected farmer.

4. Remote Sensing Results

> To access the spatial information.
> To access Farmer's spatial information and the farm-related data (if it is allowed by the Farmer)

a) Visualizing maps and bounding box's information

You can view maps and information from a previous **Special Query**:

- 1 Click on to access to the **Bounding Box Usage History**;
- 2 Click on to view the result of the **Remote Sensing analysis** from the Bounding Box of interest;
- 3 Click on **Yes** to access to the information.

You can also do it by entering BPS ID in **Get bounding box by BPS ID**

You will view the information and results from the selected Bounding Box as displayed here:

- The maps can be visualised with different layers.

- 1 Click on ;

A new section will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different Layers that are available.

- 2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;
- 3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

b) Making Special Queries

You can send special queries to NOA's API and request the Remote Sensing analysis through **Draw Bounding Box**.

For creating bounding boxes:

You can create a bounding box by drawing it over the map through **Draw Bounding Box**;

1 Click on to activate **Draw Bounding Box**;

2 Draw the box over the map with the blue dot;

To be completed (under development).

c) Visualizing maps and accessing Farmer's parcel information

The system will automatically load the selected Farmer's parcels when getting into **Remote Sensing Results**.

You can view maps and information of a specific parcel:

You can view maps and information of a specific parcel:

1 Click on **Parcel List** ;

2 Click on to view the Parcel of interest;

You can also do it through **Search parcels**.

1 Indicate the parcel ID in **Search parcel**;

Or even though the **Select parcel** option:

- 1 Click on to activate it;
- 2 Click on the parcel of interest.

You will view the maps and information of the selected parcel as displayed here:

- The parcel information is displayed on the right side of the window;

- The maps can be visualized with different layers.

- 1 Click on ;

A new section will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different layers that are available.

- 2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;
- 3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

1.1. OSOS Forms

> To access farm detail (with farmer's permission)

a) Editing OSOS claim

You can edit and access existing / available information from the selected OSOS claim by **editing OSOS data**.

1 Click on **Next** :

You will access all the information uploaded for this Farmer and the selected year of application. For instance:

- OSOS data;
- Parcels;
- Plant Production;
- Mushroom Production;
- Forest Foraging;
- Apiculture;
- Animal Production;
- Processing;
- Trade;
- Standards;
- Organic certificate.

The screenshot shows the RECAP Farm Profile dashboard. The top navigation bar includes the RECAP logo, the user's name 'Ivan Ivanov', and the current year '2017'. A progress bar indicates the current step in the OSOS process, with Step 1 highlighted. The main content area is titled 'Edit OSOS data' and contains several input fields for farmer information:

Edit OSOS data	
Farmer's personal name:	Farmer's personal lastname:
<input type="text" value="Petar"/>	<input type="text" value="Petrovic"/>
Farmer's unique registration number of the citizens:	Contact person for organic farming:
<input type="text" value="0123456789012"/>	<input type="text" value="Para"/>
Farmer's address:	Farmer's town:
<input type="text" value="Maribla Tita 20"/>	<input type="text" value="Pandevo"/>
Farmer's municipality:	Postal code of residence:
<input type="text" value="Pandevo"/>	<input type="text" value="20000"/>
Farmer's personal tax number:	Farmer's telephone:
<input type="text" value="0123456789"/>	<input type="text" value="066123456789"/>
Farmer's personal fax number:	Farmer's farm identification number:
<input type="text" value="0000000000"/>	<input type="text" value="0000000000"/>

1.2. Data Management

> To check organic certification requirements.

a) Checking Organic certification requirement

Depending on farmer's inputs, the system decides which Organic Certification requirement apply to its fields and you will see a list of all relevant requirements that the farmer need to be compliant with.

The list that will be displayed in your screen will be similar to the following one depending on the farmer's inputs:

For each **Organic certification requirement**, you can view instructions to comply it.

- 1 Click on an **Organic certification requirement**;

You will get a description of the requirement; as well as the possibility to (i) post comment, (ii) upload/view documents, and (iii) upload/view images.

For posting a comment:

- 1 Click on 0 comments ;

The following window will appear.

Author	Comment
	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; min-height: 100px;"> <p>Post a new comment</p> </div> <div style="text-align: right; margin-top: 5px;"> <input type="button" value="Post comment"/> </div>

1 of 1

2 Write your comment;

3 Click on: .

Your comment has been posted and the number of message associated to the Icon has incremented to 1 more message.

From now, this message can be seen by you and the Farmer by clicking on the Icon.

For uploading documents or images:

1 Click on the left side of the documents icon ;

2 Fill out / Select the requested information:

- Document name;
- Description ;
- Tags ;
- Parcels ;

3 Click on to select the document / image;

4 Click on to upload the document / image.

Your document / image has been uploaded.

For viewing documents or images:

1 Click on the right side of the documents icon ;

A window will appear, displaying the uploaded documents / images.

2 Click on the document / image of your interest;

Information about the selected document / image will appear.

3 Click on:

- to download it;
- to modify information related to it;
- to delete it.

b) Self-Assessment

Back to the Data Management’s Dashboard, you can check farmer’s obligation regarding completion of Organic certification requirement through **Self-Assessment**.

- 1 Click on **Self Assesment** ;

You will get a summary of all the requested tasks and documents that are still necessary.

Must	Condition	Document	Start date	Deadline	CC/Rule	Inspector	Self compliance / compliance
Yes					Organic Plant Production		X X
Yes					Group Of Producers for Plant		X X
Yes					Mushroom Production		X X
Yes					Wild Plants		X X
Yes					Apiculture		X X
Yes					Group Of Producers for Apiculture		X X
Yes					Animal Production		X X
Yes					Group Of Producers for Animal		X X
Yes					Processing		X X
Yes					Trade		X X

c) Greening Calculator

You can check greening rules through **Greening Calculator**

- 1 Click on **Greening Calculator** ;

You will get the result about the declared sub parcels and their corresponding greening calculation. They will be based on the data entered already into the system.

Greening Calculator for parcels
Total area: 539368.3569685259
Min crop area is less than 5% of total area. Crop Code that fails condition is: 5

Crop Name	Values
5	0.00 %
15	0.77 %

d) Filtering by parcels

You can view the O. C. requirement applied to a specific parcel by using the Filter to select any specific parcel:

e) Providing Farmer's with documents/images

You can provide Farmer's with documents or images related to O. C. requirements through **Other documents**.

- 1 Click on **Other documents** ;

The below windows will be displayed.

- 2 Click on the left side of the documents icon ;
- 3 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document name;
 - Description ;
 - Tags ;
 - Parcels ;
- 4 Click on **Choose media** to select the document / image;
- 5 Click on **Upload media** to upload the document / image.

Your document / image has been uploaded.

1.3. User Documents

> To view / search Farmer's documents (if it is allowed by the Farmer)

a) Searching documents

You can perform searches with key words within the Farmer's documents uploaded.

- 1 Enter your key words in **Search My Documents**;
- 2 Click on Enter.

The result of your search will be displayed.

b) Advanced Search

You can perform specific searches with labels.

- 1 Click on **Advanced Search** ;

New functionalities will appear.

For each of the following categories, you will be able to specify your searches:

- Rules
- Tasks
- Tags
- Parcels
- Types

- 2 Click on each one and select the ones you want putting a mark ;

The criteria of your search will be applied and the corresponding documents will be displayed.

1.4. Work Diary

> To view Farmer's Work Diary (if it is allowed by the Farmer)

a) Viewing Farmer's Work Diary

You will have access to the complete information registered in the Farmer's Work Diary.

You will have access to it only if it has previously been made visible by the farmer.

5. Training Guide for PAYING AGENCIES

5.1. Brief description of users

Paying Agencies can use RECAP to retrieve valuable information in order to optimize and improve the selection of farms to be inspected on Cross Compliance and Greening rules. They can also use RECAP for communication with the farmers in order to prevent breaches of the rules and respond to farmers' requests for support.

5.2. Differences between countries

Regarding the user profile of Paying Agency, the RECAP Platform is offering the same functions and services to Greece, Spain, Lithuania and U.K.

Paying Agencies	Dashbord's Options				
	Inspectors	Farmers	My Documents	Messages	Maps
GREECE	√	√	√	√	√
SPAIN	√	√	√	√	√
LITHUANIA	√	√	√	√	√
UK	√	√	√	√	√

In Serbia, the process is different.

Paying Agencies	Dashbord's Options		
	Inspection Forms	Inspections	Maps
SERBIA	√	√	√

5.3. Functions and services - for Paying Agencies.

5.3.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Paying Agencies

- (PA) A. Processing CAP Declaration
- (PA) B. Communicating with users and accessing the information of the CAP declaration
- (PA) C. Extracting information from the RECAP Database for reporting issues

(PA) A. Processing CAP Declaration

A1. Managing Inspectors' privileges [=> INSPECTORS] (only for the administrator of the PA platform) [+ Paying Agents / new function for admin]

- > Giving inspector privileges to a user account through **Become Inspector**;
- > Tacking back inspector privileges to a user account through **Remove Inspector**;

A2. Assigning farmers to be inspected to the inspectors [=> INSPECTORS]

- > Managing inspection of an Inspector through **Manage Inspections**;
- > Attributing new inspection to an inspector through **Add BPS**;
- > Removing inspection to an inspector through **Unsign**;

A3. Accessing Farm Inspection History [=> FARMERS]

- > Viewing the List of Inspections for a Farmer by selecting the corresponding BPS year (e.g. 2016);

(PA) B. Communicating with users and accessing the information of the CAP declaration

B1. Searching documents [=> MY DOCUMENTS]

- > Searching documents in the system through **Search My Documents**;
- > Specifying searches with labels through **Advanced Search**;

B2. Providing Farmers and Inspectors with documents [=> MY DOCUMENTS]

- > Uploading and tagging documents through **Add new / Edit media**;

B3. Exchanging directly with Farmers [=> MESSAGES]

- > Accessing a specific Farmer's messages through **View Messages**;
- > Sending a message to a specific Farmer through **View Messages**;

B4. Accessing the spatial information [=> MAPS]

- > Visualizing maps and bounding's information through **Maps**;

(PA) C. Extracting information from the RECAP Database for reporting issues

C1. Extracting the
desired statistics

C1. Extracting the desired statistics (under construction)

5.3.2. Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions

As **Paying Agency**, in Greece, Spain, Lithuania and U.K., you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

1. Inspectors
2. Farmers
3. My Documents
4. Messages
5. Maps

1. Inspectors

- > To manage inspectors' privileges.
- > To assign farmers / BPS to Inspectors.

a) Managing inspectors' privileges (only for the administrator of the PA platform)

This functionality is exclusively for the administrator of the PA platform.

From the list of Users / Inspectors, you can manage inspector privileges to a user account through **Become Inspector / Remove Inspector**.

- For giving inspector privileges to a user:

- 1 Click on **Become Inspector** for the user you want to give inspector privileges;

A window "Creating Inspector" will appear.

- 2 Click on **Yes** to confirm the giving of inspector privileges to the selected user;

From now, this user will have Inspector Privileges.

- For removing inspector privileges from a user:

- 1 Click on **Remove Inspector** for the user you want to remove inspector privileges;
- 2 Click on **Yes** to confirm the remove of inspector privileges from the selected user;

From now, this user will not have any more Inspector Privileges.

b) Managing inspections

From the list of Inspectors, you can assign and remove the inspections through **Manage Inspections**.

For each Inspector, you can manage their inspections:

- 1 Click on **Manage Inspections**

You will see the list of Inspections assigned to the selected Inspector and if the corresponding Farm detail is available.

- For assigning an inspection:

- 1 Click on **Add BPS** to access to the BPS List;
- 2 Click on **Add** to assign a new inspection to the Inspector;

A window “Edit Inspection” will appear.

You have the possibility to specify the type of inspection putting a mark in the corresponding **Type** (e.g. Eligibility).

- 3 Click on **Save** ;

The selected inspection has been assigned to the Inspector.

- For removing an inspection:

- 1 Click on **Unsign** to remove an inspection from the Inspector;
- 2 Click on **Yes** to confirm the removal of this inspection from the Inspector.

The selected inspection has been removed from the inspections attributed to the Inspector.

2. Farmers

> To access Farm Inspection History.

a) Viewing Inspection History

You can access to the Inspection History of each Farmer that has registered to the RECAP Platform.

1 Click on **View Inspection History** for the farmer you want to see its Inspection History;

#	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	
1			alafarga@entusa.es	View Inspection History
2	Alejandro	Spain	test_es@example.com	View Inspection History
3	Jose Angel	Garraca	jjgarraca@entusa.es	View Inspection History
4			skimic9467@gmail.com	View Inspection History
5			jedan@example.com	View Inspection History
6			1@example.com	View Inspection History
7			212@example.com	View Inspection History
8			231243@example.com	View Inspection History
9			ccc@ccc.com	View Inspection History
10			proba_es@example.com	View Inspection History

You will access to the List of Inspections of the selected Farmer.

2 Click on the **BPS year** you want to consult;

List of Inspections for Alejandro Spain

2017

You will access to the Results of the BPS year that display the status for each CC Rules.

Inspection Profile - Step 01

CC Rules	Select status from the list
GAEC 1 : Establishment of buffer strips along watercourses	PENDING
GAEC 2 : Water abstraction	PENDING
GAEC 3 : Groundwater	PENDING
GAEC 4 : Providing minimum soil cover	PENDING
GAEC 5 : Minimising soil erosion	PENDING
GAEC 6 : Maintaining the level of organic matter in soil	PENDING
GAEC 7 : Landscapes	PENDING
SMR 1 : Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs)	PENDING
SMR 2 : Wild birds	PENDING
SMR 3 : Habitats and species	PENDING
SMR 10 : Plant Protection Products (PPPs)	PENDING
None : None	PENDING

3. My Documents

- > To search documents.
- > To provide Farmers and Inspectors with documents.

a) Searching documents

You can perform searches with key words within auxiliary materials you have uploaded.

- 1 Enter your key words in **Search My Documents**;
- 2 Click on Enter.

The result of your search will be displayed.

b) Advanced Search

You can perform specific searches with labels.

- 1 Click on **Advanced Search** ;
- New functionalities will appear.
- 2 Click on **Types** and select the ones you want putting a mark ;

The result of your search will be displayed.

c) Adding a new document

You can upload documents through **Add new**.

- 1 Click on
- 2 Fill out / Select the requested information:
 - Document Name;
 - Description;
 - Tags.

You have the possibility to **tag** documents putting marks in the relevant tags.

- 3 Click on to select the document;
- 4 Click on to create the document.

Your document has been created.

d) Labelling documents

You can tag documents anytime you want.

- 1 Click on the document you want to tag;
- 2 Click on ;
- 3 Indicate / Modify the tags you want to connect to this document by adding / removing them;
- 4 Click on to save modifications.

The document is now tagged according to the indicated information.

4. Messages

> To exchange directly with Farmers and Inspectors

a) Viewing exchanges with users

You can access to your exchanges with other users (Farmers and Inspectors) through **View Messages**.

From the list of users:

- 1 Click on **View Messages** for the user of interest;

Information will appear on the top of the window.

a) Answering and sending messages to users

You can answer or send a message to a user (Farmers and Inspectors) through **View Messages**.

- 1 Fill out the requested information:
 - Title of your message;
 - Content of your message.

No messages

Enter a title

Post a new message

Send

[Upload Media](#)

You can attach a document to your message / answer.

- 2 Click on **Upload Media** and select the document you want to join;
- 2 Click on **Send**.

Your answer / message has been sent to the selected user.

5. Maps

> To access to the spatial information.

a) Visualizing maps and bounding box's information

You can view maps and information from a previous **Special Query**:

- 1 Click on to access to the **Bounding Box Usage History**;
- 2 Click on to view the result of the **Remote Sensing analysis** from the Bounding Box of interest;

- 3 Click on **Yes** to access to the information.

You can also do it by entering BPS ID in **Get bounding box by BPS ID**

You will view the information and results from the selected Bounding Box as displayed here:

- The maps can be visualised with different layers.

- 1 Click on ;

A new section will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different Layers that are available.

- 2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;
- 3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

b) Making Special Queries

You can send special queries to NOA's API and request the Remote Sensing analysis through **Draw Bounding Box**.

For creating bounding boxes:

You can create a bounding box by drawing it over the map through **Draw Bounding Box**;

- 1 Click on to activate **Draw Bounding Box**;
- 2 Draw the box over the map with the blue dot;

To be completed (under development).

5.4. Specific functions and services - for Paying Agencies in Serbia

In Serbia, since the RECAP Platform will be used for checking the compliance with organic certification requirements instead of checking CC Rules and presenting CAP declaration, Paying Agency will have a role relatively different than the one from the other participating countries.

Serbian Paying Agencies will ensure the reliability of organic certification which is a central part of the process.

Indeed, instead of the Services and Functions described in the previous section 5.3, the RECAP Platform is offering different Services and Functions for Serbian Paying Agencies as described in this section.

5.4.1. Description of the Work Flows and Services for Serbian Paying Agencies

(SPA) A. Inspecting OSOS Declaration

(SPA) A. Inspecting OSOS Declaration:

A1. Selecting Farmer and OSOS year for inspection [=> FARMERS]

- > Accessing Farmers' data by **View OSOS History**;
- > Viewing the List of OSOS for a Farmer by selecting the corresponding **OSOS year (e.g. 2016)**.

A2. Accessing Farmer and Parcels information [=> FARMER FORMS]

- > Accessing information from prior declarations by selecting the corresponding **OSOS year (e.g. 2016)**.
- > Viewing parcels' information through **View Geometry, View Sections and View Location**.

A3. Accessing the spatial information and the farm-related data [=> MAPS]

- > Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information needed for the inspection process through **Search parcels / Parcel List / Select parcel**;

A4. Viewing Farmer Messages and exchanging directly with them. [=> FARMER MESSAGES]

- > Viewing messages from the selected Farmer;
- > Accessing messages sent by Certification Bodies to the selected Farmer.
- > Sending an email to the Farmer through **Send email**;

5.4.2. Description of the Dashboard's options and their functions

As **Serbian Paying Agency**, you have access to a Dashboard that displays all options and functions of the RECAP platform developed for this User Profile:

- 1. Farmers
 - 1.1. Farmer Forms
 - 1.2. Farmers
 - 1.3. Maps
 - 1.4. Farmer Messages

1. Farmers

> To select Farmer and OSOS year for inspection.

a) Viewing OSOS History / Closing Farmer Forms

You can have access to the Farmers' data by viewing OSOS history.

- 1 Click on [View OSOS History](#) ;
- 2 Click on the **OSOS year** of interest (e.g. 2017).

You will have access to some information from the Farmer and the selected OSOS year.

RECAP Inspections Dashboard

Inspector Inspector Spain

Enter query to filter results

#	Year of Application	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	Date	
1	2016			bcasado@iniciativas-innovadoras.es	2017-09-07	Open Inspection Forms
2	2015			bcasado@iniciativas-innovadoras.es	2017-09-25	Open Inspection Forms
3	2017			bcasado@iniciativas-innovadoras.es	2017-09-07	Open Inspection Forms
4	2017			ccc@ccc.com	2017-08-23	Open Inspection Forms
5	2017	Alejandro	Spain	test_es@example.com	2017-08-22	Open Inspection Forms

1 of 1

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1.1. Farmer Forms

> To access Farmer and Parcels information.

a) Viewing Parcels' information

You will be able to see the parcels information such as:

- Geometry trough **View Geometry**;
- Sections trough **View Sections**;
- Location trough **View Location**.

Inspection Profile - Step 01

OSOS: [Progress Bar] Step 1

Line	Parcel name	Cadaster number	Cadaster municipality	Cultivation area	Cultivation area unit	Product type			
1	Popovica	1234789	Sremoka Kamenica	280.00	m2	Horse-radish	View Geometry	View Sections	View Location
2	Kod starog hrasta	123456	Bačka Palanka	950.00	m2	Tomato	View Geometry	View Sections	View Location
3	Begremanra	3456789	Bačka Palanka	800.00	m2	Cucumber	View Geometry	View Sections	View Location
4	Njivica na braju	654321	Olovac	250.00	m2	Broom-corn	View Geometry	View Sections	View Location

Previous

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1.3. Maps

> To access to the spatial information and the farm-related data

a) Visualizing maps and accessing parcel's information

The system will automatically load the Farmer's parcels when getting into **Maps**.

You can view maps and information of a specific parcel:

- 1 Click on **Parcel List** ;
- 2 Click on to view the Parcel of interest;

You can also do it through **Search parcels**.

- 1 Indicate the parcel ID in **Search parcel**;

Or even though the **Select parcel** option:

- 1 Click on to activate it;
- 2 Click on the parcel of interest.

You will view the maps and information of the selected parcel as displayed here:

- The parcel information is displayed on the right side of the window;

- The maps can be visualized with different layers.

- 1 Click on ;

A new part will appear on the left side of the window. You will have access to the different Layers that are available.

- 2 Select / Unselect the layers you want to display;

- 3 Adjust the visibility of each layer with its cursor.

1.4. Farmer Messages

> To view Farmer Messages and exchange directly with them.

a) Viewing Farmer's messages from the selected farmer

You can view all the Farmer's messages (e.g. the ones sent to you by the farmer, the ones sent by Certification Bodies to the farmer...) from the selected farmer, when entering to **Farmer Messages**.

b) Sending messages to farmers

You can send a message to a farmer:

- 1 Fill out the requested information:
 - Title of your message;
 - Content of your message.

You can attach a document to your message.

- 2 Click on **Upload Media** and select the document you want to join;
- 2 Click on **Send**.

Your message has been sent to the selected farmer.

6. APPENDIXES